

HEAVY METALS IN LIP PRODUCTS AND THEIR ASSOCIATED RISK – AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW

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RESUMO

De acordo com as autoridades reguladoras, os cosméticos devem ser seguros para a saúde humana e devem ter uma avaliação de segurança, incluindo a consideração do perfil toxicológico de todos os ingredientes. Os batons são preparações cosméticas aplicadas repetidamente e diretamente nas membranas mucosas labiais. Assim, os metais em batons constituem uma fonte de exposição crônica e podem causar efeitos adversos à saúde. O objetivo geral deste estudo foi apresentar uma correlação entre os metais pesados presentes em cosméticos para uso na mucosa labial e os riscos à saúde apresentados pela

exposição a essas substâncias. Trata-se de uma revisão de literatura realizada entre os meses de março de 2023 a junho de 2023. Os resultados descritos neste estudo mostram que os cosméticos labiais, por serem produtos para uso oral, podemos considerar que a ingestão do produto é quase certa. A presença de elementos metálicos tóxicos, e apesar da legislação existente no órgão de saúde brasileiro que trata de cosméticos, também é necessária uma ferramenta legislativa que considere os elementos metálicos em cosméticos para garantir a preservação da saúde pública. É possível concluir que o conhecimento de possíveis contaminantes em produtos labiais e a toxicidade dessas substâncias são ferramentas importantes para avaliar a segurança desses produtos cosméticos, o uso contínuo desses cosméticos contaminados pode resultar no aumento de alguns teores de metais no corpo humano além dos limites aceitáveis. Essas descobertas exigem programas de testes regulares obrigatórios para verificar a concentração de metais em produtos cosméticos.

Palavras-chave: Metais pesados; Contaminantes.

ABSTRACT

According to regulatory authorities, cosmetics must be safe for human health and must have a safety assessment, including consideration of the toxicological profile of all ingredients. Lipsticks are cosmetic preparations applied repeatedly and directly to the labial mucous membranes. Thus, metals in lipsticks constitute a source of chronic exposure and can cause adverse health effects. The general objective of this study was to present a correlation between heavy metals present in cosmetics for use on the labial mucosa and the health risks presented by exposure to these substances. This is a literature review carried out between the months of March 2023 and June 2023. The results described in this study show that lip cosmetics, as they are products for oral use, we can consider that the ingestion of the product is almost certain. The presence of toxic metallic elements, and despite existing legislation from the Brazilian health agency that deals with cosmetics, it is also necessary to have a legislative tool that considers metallic elements in cosmetics to ensure the preservation of public health. It is possible to conclude that the knowledge of possible contaminants in lip

products and the toxicity of these substances are important tools to evaluate the safety of these cosmetic products, continuous use of these contaminated cosmetics can result in an increase in some levels of metals in the human body beyond acceptable limits. These findings call for mandatory regular testing programs to verify the concentration of metals in cosmetic products.

Keywords: Lipsticks; Heavy metals; Contaminants.

1. Introduction

A cosmetic product is considered any substance or pharmaceutical preparation placed in contact with one of the external parts of the human body (epidermis, capillary system, nails, lips and external genitalia) or that can be applied to the teeth and/or mucous membranes of the oral cavity, and may also be used exclusively or mainly for the purpose of cleaning, perfumery, protection, change of appearance, correction of body odors and maintenance of surfaces in good condition (OYEDEJI et al., 2011). Cosmetics can be mixtures of some surfactants, oils, actives and other ingredients that must have properties and the ability to guarantee efficacy, durability, stability and be safe for human use (RAO & PRATHIBA, 1998).

Brazil is a cosmetic market with great potential for the world and several factors contribute to this. These include: the source of active ingredients and raw materials, especially those of natural origin; the use of advanced and innovative technologies; advances in the regulatory area and the search for qualification.

Many cosmetics contain chemical additives to improve their performance properties and effectiveness making them more viable products. However, there has been growing concern about the addition of chemical compounds, including dioxane, formaldehyde, lead, parabens, phthalate, aluminum, arsenic, cadmium, chromium, manganese, mercury, titanium. Although these chemicals are associated with harmful effects on human health at high levels of exposure, the levels found in cosmetics, when used properly, should be below toxic concentrations.

According to regulatory authorities, cosmetics must be safe for human health under normal or reasonably foreseeable use, and for each finished product, there must be a safety assessment, including consideration of the toxicological profile of all ingredients. et al., 2016 NASIRUDEEN & AMAECHI, 2015). Despite this, some cases of adverse health effects have been reported, including more frequently allergic reactions resulting from the presence of various chemical compounds in cosmetics. Around 10,000 chemical substances can be detected in cosmetic products, and there are more than 1,000 substances that, due to their toxicological profile, cannot be used in these cosmetic products, among which several heavy metals stand out (BOCCA, PINO & ALIMONTI, FORTE, 2014; BOROWSKA & BRZÓSKA 2015; ULLAH et al., 2013).

Lipsticks are cosmetic preparations applied repeatedly and directly to the labial mucous membranes. Thus, metals in lipsticks constitute a source of chronic exposure and can cause adverse health effects. Furthermore, in the case of metal allergens, it can occur even after a short period of aesthetic use and even after the first use in the case of sensitized individuals (BOCCA, PINO & ALIMONTI, FORTE, 2014; BOROWSKA & BRZÓSKA 2015; GOH, NG & KWOK, 1989; OH et al; 2016; TRAVASSOS et al., 2011; VERHULST et al., 2014; ZAKARIA, 2015).

For these reasons, in recent years there has been a growing interest in lipsticks as a source of toxic metal exposure and unfavorable side reactions. Cosmetics are one of the products most frequently causing allergic reactions (BOCCA, PINO & ALIMONTI, FORTE, 2014; BOROWSKA & BRZÓSKA 2015; GOH, NG & KWOK, 1989; OH et al; 2016; ACKAH et al., 2015; FARRAG & ABU, 2015, GAO et al., 2015; IBRAHIM et al., 2016; IWEGBUE et al., 2016; IWEGBUE, 2015; KALICANIN & VELIMIROVIC, 2016; NOUIOUI et al., 2016; BASKETTER et al., 2003, SMITH, CLARK & WILKINSON, 2015), however, little attention has been given to metals in these preparations as causes of allergic processes. Thus, this present study provides an overview of lipsticks as a source of metal exposure.

Thus, the general objective of this work is to present a correlation between the heavy metals present in cosmetics for use on the labial mucosa and the health risks presented by exposure to these substances.

2. Development

2.1 Methodology

This literature review was carried out between March 2023 and June 2023, with restrictions on the date of publication of the included works, papers from the last 15 years on the subject were accepted. Studies in Portuguese and English were accepted. Ongoing studies were not analyzed, being analyzed complete case-control studies, clinical trial, epidemiological and reviews on the subject available in the following databases: MEDLINE, SCIELO, SCIENCE DIRECT and VHL. Exclusion criteria were: a) articles that do not deal with the association of contaminants in cosmetics; b) articles that did not address the use of makeup on the labial mucosa; c) case reports; d) review articles that did not present data correlating heavy metals and cosmetics; e) other types of study than those listed above. An analysis of the references of each work was performed to include additional studies.

The search strategy included the terms [batom/lipstick, contaminates/contaminants, cosmetics/cosmetics, metals/metals, toxicity/toxicity] all appearing in the title and/or abstract. Corresponding terms in English were also checked. The pre-selection of studies was based on reading their title and/or abstract, and, when necessary, the full text. A search was also carried out on the current legislation for cosmetics.

2.2. Lip products

According to Law No. 6,360 of 1976, in Art. 3, V, provides that cosmetics are products that were manufactured for external use, and their purpose designates the protection and beautification of the various parts of the body. The following are considered as beautification products for external application: lipstick, lip pencils, blushes, make-up bases, facial powders, cosmetic oils, mascaras, eye shadows, eyeliners, hair dyes, hair bleaching agents, talcum powders, among others (BRASIL, 1976).

Lipstick is a cosmetic product that contains pigments, oils, waxes and emollients that apply color, which are adjusted to the desired melting point and viscosity, give texture and protection to the lips, as with most other types of makeup, lipstick it is typically, but not exclusively, used by women. Some lipsticks also have a protective purpose, to add color and hydration. The product consists of a stick-shaped material, inside a tubular container, usually around 10 mm in diameter and 50 mm in length (BALSAM & SAGARIN, 2008). According to Balsam and Sagarin (2008), lipsticks must have the following characteristics:

- a) It should be smooth and easy to apply and leave a thin film on the lips;
- b) It must be non-irritating and non-toxic;
- c) Must have slow wear, moisture, color and shine.
- d) It should be free of grit and provide hydration and plasticity.
- e) It must be innocuous both internally and externally.

The main components present in lipstick formulations are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Lipstick components and functions.

Component	Function
Solid Waxes (beeswax, carnauba wax, candelilla wax)	provide hardness
softening agents	Lubricates lipstick after application
(wool fat, lanolin, lecithin, cocoa butter)	Dispense the pigment and give the lipstick a high gloss
Oil (castor oil, liquid paraffin)	color
coloring agents	give aroma

Source: The author (2023).

The proportion of ingredients used in lipstick formulations determines the final characteristics of the product. In general, they are made from an oily vehicle comprising fat or oil hardened to a desired consistency with waxes of various types which also serve to raise the melting point and improve physical stability. The color is normally provided by insoluble pigments, such as some intensely colored metals, generally used finely dispersed in the oily vehicle, and one or more different dyes may be associated in the formulation, many of these ingredients are described in Table 1 (BATISTA, 2017).

With all this it is important to point out that with constant growth and the integration of new proposals and different brands, beauty products, mainly lipstick, gain a margin of development proportional to its stimulation with its final consumer, through beauty advertisements among others.

According to Batista (2017), there is an increasing number of people using makeup on a daily basis, with different aspects, some for aesthetic reasons, others for social reasons, others for formalities, work, and others because they like it. to enhance the look, for this reason they acquire these types of products with a certain frequency. Associated with this growing use of lipstick, we can consider that there is an increase in the offer of these products, including the emergence of different brands that present different options for coloring and textures, which can lead to the commercialization of products that do not meet the quality standards and can generate user health risks.

2.3. Contaminants in lip products

Most of the information needed to assess the potential risk of a cosmetic product results from knowledge of the ingredients that make up its formula. They are the ones who can be directly responsible for any local and systemic effect. However, the formulation of the product can also interfere, as it facilitates the total or

partial absorption of the ingredients. In addition, possible interactions may occur, resulting from the association between the components of the formulation, which may influence the potential risk of a product (BRASIL, 2012).

According to Bocca et al. (2014), between the years 1989 and 2008, articles on metals in cosmetics were rarely published, as can be seen in Figure 1. On the other hand, between 2009 and 2013, the number of published works increased significantly from of the year 2011. The categories of cosmetic products and the respective publications can be seen in Figure 1 (BOCCA et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Articles published over the years and the respective cosmetic product category (Adapted from BOCCA et al., 2014).

The Brazilian Association of Personal Hygiene, Perfumery and Cosmetic Industry (ABIHPEC) indicates that Brazil is among one of the biggest consumers of products with cosmetic purpose, some of the main related products are perfumes, deodorants, sun protection products and products men, occupying the fifth ranking as the largest makeup product market, a considerable

placement given the vast field of personal hygiene and cosmetics industries that the country has (ABIHPEC, 2016).

Constant growth and the integration of new proposals to serve the consumer and the emergence of different brands of beauty products, mainly lipstick. Due to this growth, the risk of the presence of contaminants in these products is increasing.

The sources of exposure and/or contamination by heavy metals in cosmetic products can be divided into two main categories. Firstly, there are the sources of metals destined for intentional use in the production of cosmetics, which include pigments, UV filters and preservatives, as well as antiperspirant, antibacterial and antifungal agents. Occurring mainly exposure to metals such as chromium, iron, aluminum, zinc, titanium, strontium, copper, silver and gold. The type of metal will vary according to its application in the formulation and the exposure according to the concentration, which should vary according to the regulatory laws of each country. The other important category of exposure/contamination to metals in cosmetics is unintentional source impurities resulting from the use of raw materials (plants and minerals) and water contaminated with metals, as well as the use of metal-coated apparatus during production of cosmetics (FDA, 2017).

During the various stages of cosmetics production, undesirable constituents that can easily be present as sources of contamination include lead, cadmium, aluminum, mercury and arsenic. It is important to highlight that the same metal can be present in a cosmetic product due to its intentional use and also present itself as an impurity (BOCCA et al., 2014). Table 2 presents different metals intentionally used in the production of cosmetic products.

Table 2: List of metals intentionally used in the production of cosmetics.

Metal	Goal	Product	Reference
Chromium, Titanium, Iron,	hair coloring	Paints and Shampoos	KANG et al., 2006

Silver, Copper, Cobalt, Bismuth			
Chromium oxide and chromium hydroxide	dyes	eye shadows	KANG et al., 2006
Chrome	Dye	Lipstick	ZAKARIA & HO, 2015
Iron oxide	Dye	eye makeup	KANG & LEE, 2006; ZAZARIA & HO, 2015
Zinc, copper, iron and chromium	Durability	Cosmetics in general	BOCCA et al., 2014
Titanium dioxide, zinc oxide and barium sulfate	UV filters	sunscreens	FAGE et al., 2016
Mercury	Preservatives and skin lighteners	Makeup and creams	ADAWA & OBERG, 2013
Aluminum	Dyes, antiperspirants and astringents	Makeup, aftershave, astringent lotions, mouthwash, deodorants, bath salts	MARINOVICH et al., 2014

Source: The author (2023).

The different inorganic metallic compounds are used in the production of cosmetics, many of them as dyes (chromium, titanium, iron), hair dyes and shampoos (silver, copper, iron, cobalt, bismuth). Substances such as chromium oxide, chromium hydroxide and iron oxide are used as dyes in the preparation of

cosmetics applied to the eyelids of the eyes (eye shadows), some other essential metals (zinc, copper, iron and chromium) can also be added to cosmetics during production in order to improve pigment quality; however, if they are present in excessive amounts, they can be a cause of skin irritation and other adverse effects (ATZ, 2008).

Nanoparticles of titanium dioxide, zinc oxide and barium sulfate are used as physical ultraviolet filters in skin care and protection products (KANG et al., 2006). Mercury compounds are used as preservatives in eye makeup products. Due to the ability of mercury to inactivate tyrosinase (the main melanin-forming enzyme), in some countries mercury is used in skin lightening creams (ADAWA & OBERG, 2013; MARINOVICH et al., 2014). Aluminum, in addition to its use as a dye, is also used in antiperspirants, as it is able to block sweat glands. Furthermore, due to the astringent properties (precipitation of blood proteins) allowing the inhibition of microvascular bleeding, aluminum compounds are used in aftershave preparations, other astringent facial lotions, bath salts, and mouthwashes. ; BOCCA et al., 2014; FAGE et al., 2016)..

2.4. Aluminum (Al) and aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃)

Aluminum is a chemical element with the symbol Al, being considered a metallic element, it has atomic number 13 and its atomic mass 27 u (KROSCHWITZ, 1999).

Alumina, also known as aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃), is its dehydrated form. This compound is related to the production of colors which come from small impurities of heavy metals. The most common natural form of alumina is its crystalline form. This water-insoluble inorganic solid can form various other crystalline phases and also an amorphous form. Each phase has a unique crystalline structure and varies in chemical properties, such as its acid-base reaction rate. Aluminum hydroxide, also known as hydrated alumina, is most commonly found as a polymorphic mineral (a component of the aluminum ore known as bauxite) (KROSCHWITZ, 1999; BALAN et al., 2013).

Aluminum oxide also known as alumina is reported to function in cosmetics as an abrasive, absorbent, anti-caking agent, bulking agent and opacifying agent;

aluminum hydroxide is reported to function as a buffering agent, corrosion inhibitor and pH adjuster (SLANIN et al., 1984).

Aluminum in the form of aluminum hydroxide is poorly absorbed orally or by inhalation and is essentially not absorbed dermally in healthy humans. Usually orally, approximately 0.1% to 0.6% of aluminum is absorbed. It is believed that the main mechanism of absorption occurs in the gastrointestinal tract system through passive diffusion of paracellular pathways. Absorbed aluminum is distributed to all organs, but mainly in bone and lung tissues, its excretion occurs in the urine and, to a lesser extent, in the bile (SLANINA et al, 1984, DOMINGO, GOMEZ & LLOBE, 1991, TESTOLIN, et al., 1996).

Dermal absorption can occur through the aluminum salts used in antiperspirants (manufacture of aerosols) that form a precipitate of denatured keratin hydroxide in the cornified layer that surrounds and obstructs the opening of the sweat ducts, these mechanisms suggest that there is little or no dermal absorption of aluminum hydroxide or any other form of aluminum (YOKEL & MCNAMARA, 2001; PRIEST et al., 1996, WEBERG & BERSTAD, 1986; THORNE et al., 1987).

2.5. Arsenic (As)

Arsenic is a chemical element with the symbol As, being considered a metal, with atomic number 33 and atomic mass 75 u (EFSA, 2009).

Arsenic found as a commonly distributed element in the atmosphere, rocks, minerals, soil, water and the biosphere. Redox potential and pH are the most important factors controlling arsenic speciation. Toxicity varies with the chemical form in which it is found, and can range from essentially non-toxic to excessively toxic, depending on the following factors: oxidation state and groups attached to arsenic. Arsenic hydride, known as arsine, is considered to be the most toxic species, while arsene sugars (AsSug, found in algae) and arsenobetaine (AsB, found in fish) are considered non-toxic (EFSA, 2009).

Arsenic toxicity may be linked to its ability to block the SH group of different enzymes. The uncoupling of phosphorylation and the breakdown of essential metabolic processes, such as glucose metabolism, lead to the denaturation of different proteins (CHEN, 2009).

In cosmetics segments incorporating reddish pigments, for example, are commonly contaminated with arsenic. Some cosmetics that are colored and used for face, body, hair care and herbal cosmetics may contain relatively high amounts of this heavy metal in their formulation. This element, like other heavy metals, can accumulate in the skin and internal organs, causing toxic effects, which can be classified as topical effects (mainly contact dermatitis) or systemic effects (systemic allergic dermatitis). In addition to causing dermatological disorders, they can generate circulatory and peripheral nervous system imbalances, increase the risk of lung cancer, a possible increase in the risk of cancer of the gastrointestinal tract and urinary system (BOCCA et al., 2014; BOROWSKA & BRZOSKA, 2015). Therefore, through the simple daily use of a cosmetic applied to the labial mucosa, such as lipsticks and gloss, for example, this metal can accumulate and consequently cause toxic and harmful effects to the health of the consumer.

2.6. Cadmium (Cd)

Cadmium is a chemical element with the symbol Cd, being considered a transition metal, it has atomic number 48 and its atomic mass consists of 112.4 u, at room temperature it tends to remain in its solid state (UCKO, 1992).

According to Bocca et al. (2014), cadmium is heavily used by the cosmetics industry as a pigmentation agent, used in lipstick shadows and in the most varied cosmetics that require coloring. Cd sulfide has a yellow color and little by little if a favorable amount of the element selenium is added, it can have a color variant between shades of orange to darker tones, reaching shades close to black. The addition of cadmium (yellow) with Cr(III) oxide results in a light green tonality pigmentation, known by cadmium green industries (BOCCA et al., 2014).

After ingestion, cadmium in the body acts directly on cell proliferation, differentiation and apoptosis. These activities interact with the DNA repair mechanism, the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the induction of apoptosis. Cadmium binds to mitochondria and can inhibit cellular respiration and oxidative phosphorylation at low concentrations. This mechanism results in chromosome disturbances, DNA strand breaks, and cross-linking between DNA and protein. Cadmium can induce ROS production and result in oxidative stress. This mechanism may express the role of cadmium in organ toxicity, carcinogenicity and apoptotic cell death (RANI et al., 2015; PATRICK, 2003; JOSEPH, 2009).

2.7. Lead (Pb)

Lead is a chemical element with the symbol Pb, being considered a heavy metal, it has atomic number 82 and its atomic mass consists of 207.2 u (CDC, 1991).

Lead (Pb) is an element that occurs naturally in the earth's crust. It is widely distributed throughout the environment as it has been used in gasoline production, consumer products, product recycling, and manufacturing processes (CDC, 1991). Although important measures have been implemented in several countries to decrease environmental exposure to Pb, such as the use of unleaded gasoline, removal of lead from paint, soldering of canned foods and glazed ceramics used for food storage and preparation, it is still a major environmental health problem in specific communities and high-risk target populations (MEYER et al., 2008).

The ingestion of large amounts of lead causes intoxication by interfering with the synthesis of the heme group at the mitochondrial level and in calcium channels in nerve conduction. Lead affects virtually every system in the body, including the reproductive, neurological, hematopoietic, hepatic, and renal systems. It is well established that lead can cross the placenta during pregnancy and has been associated with intrauterine fetal death and premature births (PAPANIKOLAOU et al., 2005; COMISKEY et al., 2015; MEYER et al., 2008).

The concentration of approximately 10 µg/dl of lead in maternal blood is enough to increase the risk of hypertension in pregnancy and miscarriage. In addition, the consequences of accelerated bone loss during menopause and the decrease in estrogen production can be increased due to high levels of lead in the body (VAHTER et al., 2007; BELLINGER, 2005).

In the cosmetic industry, inorganic Pb can be found in hair dyes (such as lead acetate) and lipsticks and can be minimally absorbed by the skin, unlike organic lead, which is quickly absorbed. Studies show that dermal absorption of inorganic lead occurs at a rate of 2.9 ng/cm. Exposure to organic and inorganic compounds lead to significant contamination of lead on the skin, which may originate from cosmetics for cutaneous use (ALSAFFAR & HUSSEIN, 2014; NNOROM, IGWE & OJI-NNOROM, 2005; HARDY, WALTON & VAISHNAV, 2004).

However, lead exposure assessments have always been based on ingestion of food, water or air. Lead is generally not an ingredient in lipstick, but it can be found as an impurity in raw materials or acquired during the manufacturing process. Most recent studies emphasize that there is no safe level of exposure to lead, representing a much smaller source of exposure compared to other sources (food and water, for example), due to the amount of lipstick that is applied daily. However, it cannot be excluded that lead accumulates in the body over time and repeated application of lipsticks containing lead can lead to significant levels of exposure. The consequences of these products can only be adequately verified by conducting an exposure study to assess population risk (BELLINGER, 2008, VOLPE et al., 2012; COMISKEY et al., 2015).

2.8. Chrome (Cr)

Chromium is considered as a transition metal and heavy metal, its atomic number is 24, its atomic mass consists of 52 u, and at a temperature of around 21 and 25°C it is stable assuming its solid characteristic (UCKO, 1992).

The next most stable form is hexavalent chromium. Cr (0), Cr (III) and Cr (VI) are used commercially and are present in the environment. Cr(0) is primarily in its metallic form as a component of iron-based alloys such as stainless steel.

Trivalent chromium (Cr(III)) is mainly of geological origin and hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) is mainly derived from industrial processes but can also originate from the oxidation of natural Cr(III) by minerals. ; UCKO, 1992).

The main source of oral exposure to Cr for non-occupational human populations comes from ingestion of food and drinking water. Increased industrial applications, however, lead to a large amount of Cr released into soil, groundwater and air. The specific mechanism of chromium carcinogenicity remains unclear, however, there are data supporting the genotoxicity and mutagenicity of Cr(VI) in vivo and in vitro. Chromium in its hexavalent form is considered a procarcinogen. Cr(VI) manages to enter the cell through the mechanism of molecular mimicry as a polyatomic ion followed by its metabolic reduction to Cr(V), Cr(IV) and to the trivalent form in the final reduction (SALNIKOW & ZHITKOVICH 2008; ALEXANDER & AASETH 1995; O'BRIEN et al. 2001).

Occupational exposure usually occurs by inhalation and the lung is the main target organ, and there are also reports that exposure can occur through the skin. The widespread incidence of dermatitis noted among construction workers is attributed to their exposure to chromium present in cement, as in a study presented by Shelnutz et al., 2007.

In general, occupational and environmental exposure to compounds containing Cr (VI) is known to cause toxicity in multiple organs, such as kidney damage, allergy and asthma, and cancer of the respiratory tract in humans (COSTA, 1997). Chromium toxicity occurs through oxidation state and solubility. Cr(VI) compounds, which are powerful oxidizing agents and therefore tend to be irritating and corrosive, may be more systemically toxic than Cr(III) compounds due to similar amount and solubility (CONNETT & WETTERHAHN, 1983 ; DE FLORA et al., 1990)

The biological interaction mechanisms are still uncertain, and may be related to the ease with which Cr (VI) can pass through cell membranes and its subsequent intracellular reduction to reactive intermediates. As Cr(III) is poorly absorbed,

toxicity is mainly attributed to its Cr(VI) form. The main organs related to the absorption of this metal are the lungs and the gastrointestinal tract (DAYAN & PAINE, 2001).

2.9. Mercury (Hg)

Mercury is a chemical element with the symbol Hg, considered as a metal, its atomic number is 80, its atomic mass consists of 200.59 u (CAITO et al., 2018).

Mercury exists in both organic and inorganic forms. The inorganic form can be further subdivided into elemental mercury and mercury salts. Elementary exposures are typically from mercury-containing devices, such as thermometers, for example. Exposures to mercury salt can be observed with the ingestion of batteries or medicinal compounds with the presence of mercury in their formulation, such as laxatives. Organic mercury can also be subdivided into short-chain and long-chain compounds. Exposure to organic mercury usually occurs through eating contaminated seafood, hair dyes or even other skin contact cosmetics (CAITO et al., 2018; BJORKLUND, 2017).

Long-term exposure to mercury becomes harmful to health, this exposure when it reaches the systemic circulation, the transport of this substance will occur through organic anions in the kidneys occurs through the kidney of the proximal tubules (HAZELHOFF, BULACIO & TORRES, 2012 ; HULTMAN & ENESTROM, 1986).

2.10. Manganese (Mn)

Manganese is a chemical element with the symbol Mn, considered as a transition metal, its atomic number is 25, its atomic mass consists of 55 u (GUNIER et al. 2013).

Manganese is an essential metal that plays a key role in brain development and functioning, it is also widely used in the processing of other metals. It is an essential trace element, found in a wide variety of food sources, including meat, fish, poultry, dried fruit, tea and nuts. Environmental exposure to Mn can lead to

accumulation in the basal ganglia and the development of Parkinson-like disorders (BORGESSE et al. 2013; GUNIER et al. 2013).

Manganese is a naturally occurring trace element essential for human development and brain function and other biological processes. As a trace element, Mn is taken up with the diet (mainly with grains, fruits, vegetables, tea) and, once ingested, is absorbed by the small intestine in a proportion of about 3-4%. Gastrointestinal absorption is influenced by iron metabolism: an iron deficiency increases Mn absorption through some transport proteins. When exposure occurs by inhalation, Mn is absorbed through the alveolar-capillary membrane in a percentage between 40 and 70%, its elimination is through the gastrointestinal tract through bile, intestinal mucosa and pancreatic secretion. The main excretion of Mn is carried out in the feces regardless of the route of introduction, while the portion excreted in the urine is low, about 6% of the total (DEWITT et al. 2013; LUCAS et al. 2015).

2.11. Titanium (Ti)

Titanium (Ti) is a non-essential metallic element with atomic number 22, being an insoluble compound. It is the ninth most abundant element in the Earth's crust and the seventh most abundant metal overall (BARKSDALE, 1968).

In powder form, Ti is one of the whitest substances available, making it an ingredient in a wide range of industrial and consumer products, including cosmetics and sunscreens. Notably, titanium is the third most used material in consumer products. The use of Ti in sunscreens makes it a more transparent vehicle, less viscous and adheres to the skin more easily (ROBICHAUD et al., 2009; HUSSAIN et al., 2012; NEWMAN, STOTLAND & ELLIS, 2009)

The widespread topical use of Ti occurs through nanoparticles which increase its use in cosmetic products, having the potential to penetrate through the stratum corneum, reach the viable layers of the skin and ultimately result in sensitization or other side effects. The permeability of the oral mucosa becomes up to 4000 times greater than that of other tissues, which would facilitate the penetration of cosmetic products applied to the oral mucosa, making exposure to this heavy

metal even more intense. Exposure to Ti in personal care products is common, but reports of clinical allergy are rare. However, evidence for possible toxic effects and risk of allergic reactions is weak.

2.12. Toxicological aspects: health risks

There are several regulatory agencies that are dedicated to the control and regulation of commercial activities, safety and quality control of cosmetics. Although there are rules and quality control tests to be followed for the manufacture of a cosmetic, these regulatory mechanisms are not fully effective, as adverse effects still persist in the population of cosmetic consumers (ALANI, DAVIS & YIANNIAS, 2013).

Faced with the emergence of the use of cosmetic products and greater exposure to the compounds in formulas for a long time and frequency, the side effects of these products become more frequent in the population. Many components present in the composition of cosmetics are also pollutants to the environment, these contaminations occurring mainly through water, representing health risks (NICOLOPOULOU-STAMATI, HENS & SASCO, 2015).

Thus, Cosmetovigilance aims to ensure the safety of cosmetic products for commercial purposes. This vigilance is very important to control potentially dangerous ingredients. Unlike drugs, there is no specific agency to assess the safety of cosmetic products, no marketing authorization with specific requirements, no assessment of the risk-benefit ratio and no guarantee of constancy from one batch to another (VIGAN & CASTELAIN, 2014) .

The health risks associated with the use of cosmetic products are currently an emerging public health problem, where about 12% of users in the general population have had undesirable effects with one or more cosmetic products in the last nine years (NICOLOPOULOU-STAMATI , HENS & SASCO, 2015; VIGAN & CASTELAIN, 2014).

The presence of components in the formulation of cosmetic products, such as heavy metals, has the potential to cause side effects and its consequences can

vary from a simple mild hypersensitivity reaction to an anaphylactic process or even lethal intoxication, since there is a series of adverse reactions caused by cosmetics. Most adverse reactions are irritating, however, type IV hypersensitivity, contact urticaria, photosensitization, pigmentary disorders, hair and nail damage, paronychia, acneiform eruptions, folliculitis, and exacerbation of an established dermatosis may also occur. The body areas most affected by adverse reactions attributed to the use of cosmetics are the head, lips and neck, and irritant dermatitis is the most common type of complication (DRAELOS, 2015; ALANI, DAVIS & YIANNIAS 2013; PARK & ZIPPIN, 2014; WOLF et al., 2001).

Metals present in cosmetics can be accumulated in the skin or absorbed through this route, metals such as Ni, Co and Cr are accumulated in the stratum corneum and can cause allergic contact dermatitis, while Hg, Pb, Cd and Al pass through the layers of the skin into the bloodstream and are transported to various organs where they accumulate and exert toxic effects (STAUBER et al., 1994; LANSDOWN & SAMPSON, 1996; LIN et al., 2012, LARESE et al., 2007; FILON et al., 2009).

Although metals are present in cosmetics in very low concentrations, repeated use of these products can result in significant cumulative exposure to metals, sometimes numerous. It is worth noting that cosmetics containing metals represent a source of occupational exposure for hairdressers and beauticians, for example, due to their frequency in handling these products (FOULDS, 2006; HOSTYNEK, 2003).

Several exposure scenarios are possible for metals present in cosmetics, which can result in brief contact, as with rinse-off products (e.g., shampoos, shower gels, toothpastes) or remaining in contact with the skin for long hours, as in products leave-on products (e.g., face creams, body lotions, lipsticks), where these preparations can be applied to a large body surface area (FOULDS, 2006; HOSTYNEK, 2003).

Increased absorption can occur when cosmetics come into contact with areas such as the genital region, as well as the skin of children, in whom absorption

through the skin is greater than in adults. In the case of metals present in lipsticks, there is a risk of oral ingestion, while the ingredients of products applied in the form of sprays can be absorbed by inhalation, exposure to the metal depends on numerous exogenous and endogenous factors that determine the permeability of the skin to them. (FOULDS, 2006; HOSTYNEK, 2003).

Metals such as nickel, chromium, cobalt and selenium accumulate mainly in the stratum corneum and can cause skin effects (eg allergic contact dermatitis).

Nickel compounds are generally soluble and diffusible, being able to penetrate the stratum corneum through skin appendages (hair follicles, sweat glands and sebaceous glands), as well as by transcellular or intracellular routes, but the penetration of this metal into the stratum corneum is slow and addresses only 1% of the amount applied to the skin. However, it should be taken into account that absorption can be altered by factors that influence skin permeability (BOCCA et al., 2014; HOSTYNEK, 2003).

At the epidermal level, the metal, being a hapten (non-protein substance, low molecular weight, alone cannot induce an immune response), binds to amino acid residues of proteins, forming metal-protein complexes capable of causing contact allergy. Allergic reactions are the most common adverse skin effect of metals in cosmetics, and nickel is the most important metal allergen in these products. Reported cases of allergy due to metals present in cosmetics were mainly caused by colored cosmetics containing nickel, cobalt and chromium (BOCCA et al., 2014; BOROWSKA & BRZÓSKA, 2015; SMITH, CLARK & WILKINSON, 2015; GOH & KWOK, 1989; OH et al., 2016; TRAVASSOS et al., 2011).

The metals mercury, cadmium, lead, aluminum and nickel are recognized for their ability to be systemically absorbed and transported to different organs, which can accumulate and cause damage to internal organs, resulting in neurological disorders; cardiovascular problems; liver, kidney and lung damage; reproductive and developmental disorders and cancers (CHAN et al., 2001; BENZ et al., 2011).

From these toxicological considerations, it is important to highlight that the legislative document structures that regulate cosmetics are essential to ensure safe levels of contaminants in cosmetics, in order to ensure the integrity of the health of users.

2.13. Regulatory aspects

Documentary structures that regulate cosmetics differ significantly between countries and are far from harmonized. In general, cosmetic products are subject to regulatory controls in all countries, with the aim of ensuring the safety of using the products and avoiding adverse effects on the health of consumers. It is important to highlight that the lack of harmonization between markets can lead to customs barriers (RATH & CANAES, 2009).

2.13.1. Brazilian legislation for cosmetic products

The “Guide for the Safety Assessment of Cosmetic Products”, which was first published in 2003, describes that the safety assessment of cosmetic products must precede the placing of the cosmetic product on the market. The company is responsible for the safety of the cosmetic product, as guaranteed by the Term of Responsibility presented at the time of product regularization, where the company declares that it has supporting data that attest to its effectiveness and safety. Since the cosmetic product is freely accessible to the consumer, it must be safe under normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use. The pursuit of this security must permanently incorporate the advancement of the state of the art in cosmetic science (BRASIL, 2012a).

2.13.2. RDC n° 211 of July 14, 2005

According to RDC n° 211, of July 14, 2005, it establishes the Definition and Classification of Personal Hygiene Products, Cosmetics and Perfumes. Personal Hygiene Products, Cosmetics and Perfumes, are preparations made from natural or synthetic substances, for external use in the various parts of the human body, skin, capillary system, nails, lips, external genital organs, teeth and mucous membranes of the cavity oral, with the sole purpose of cleaning, perfuming,

changing the appearance or correcting body odors, and protecting, keeping it in good condition. There are different classifications for these products which are:

- Grade 1 products: are personal hygiene products, cosmetics and perfumes, which, due to their basic or elementary properties, whose proof is not initially necessary and do not require detailed information regarding their mode of use and their respective restrictions, due to the characteristics its intrinsic properties, such as, for example, some cosmetics mentioned in the list of grade 1 products, deals with products such as lip balm and lip gloss (not for photoprotective purpose), facial concealer (not for protective purpose), eyeliner for lips, eyes and eyebrows, among others. others.
- Grade 2 products: are personal hygiene products, cosmetics and perfumes, whose formulations have specific indications and evidence, as well as their mode of use, information regarding care and restrictions. For example, some cosmetics mentioned in the grade 2 list, including: children's lipstick and children's lip gloss, children's blush/rouge, children's cologne, anti-dandruff/hair loss conditioners and children's conditioners, deodorant for intimate use, among others.

It is possible to observe that there are different classifications regarding personal hygiene products, grade 1 products do not require detailed information when compared to grade 2 products, which can provide products with the presence of contaminants in their formulation, presenting a risk to health of the final consumer, since these products are for cutaneous use, which allows considerable permeation, which may cause harmful effects, such as the presence of heavy metals commonly correlated mainly to grade 1 products, due to approval by the inspection body being less rigid, therefore, it is expected that these products do not present an imminent risk to the health of the buyer.

2.13.3. RDC N° 48, October 25, 2013

Approves the Technical Regulation of Good Manufacturing Practices for Personal Hygiene Products, Cosmetics and Perfumes, and takes other measures. RDC N° 48/13 through its quality management the principles to be followed from the

beginning of the production of cosmetics, personal hygiene and perfume to the commercialization process. Through the context discussed, follow the Basic Requirements of Good Manufacturing Practices:

“Manufacturing processes must be clearly defined, systematically reviewed, and show that they are capable of manufacturing products within the required quality standards, meeting the respective specifications”

“Critical steps in the manufacturing processes and any significant modifications must be systematically controlled and, where possible, validated”

“The manufacturing areas must be provided with the necessary infrastructure to carry out the activities, including:

- I. Trained and qualified personnel;*
- II. Adequate facilities and spaces;*
- III. Appropriate services and equipment;*
- IV. Appropriate labels, packaging and materials;*
- V. Approved instructions and procedures;*
- VI. Appropriate deposits;*
- VII. Adequate personnel, laboratory and equipment for quality control.”*

This RDC aims at quality management, from the first stage of cosmetic manufacturing, its critical stages and after its validation, with this it seeks to portray the possible achievements of the appropriate activities such as training, checking of services and materials and the necessary clothing equipment, where

they influence the quality of the final product, in which a safe and effective product will be presented to the consumer.

2.13.4. RDC N° 47, March 16, 2006

Approves the Technical Regulation List of Allowed Ultraviolet Filters for Personal Hygiene Products, Cosmetics and Perfumes. The Resolution provides for the prevention of ultraviolet filters, and the substances that are incorporated into sun protection products, where they are intended to filter ultraviolet rays, with the aim of protecting the skin from the harmful effects caused by the same.

As an example, the Methyl Sulfate of N, N, N-trimethyl – 4- (2, oxoborn – 3 – ylidenemethyl) anilinium Camphor benzalkonium methosulfate, which presents 6% as the maximum concentration authorized by current Brazilian legislation.

The search for prevention with ultraviolet filters, has been breaking several paradigms regarding the improvements of their filters and percentage that are determined for the filters to provide protection, and that many of these formulations at the time of their preparation do not exceed the pre-established limit.

2.13.5. RDC N° 29, June 1, 2012

Approves the Mercosur Technical Regulation on the “List of Substances with Preservative Action Allowed for Personal Hygiene Products, Cosmetics and Perfumes” and makes other provisions. All personal hygiene products, cosmetics and perfumes must be guaranteed through normal or foreseeable conditions of use. It is essential to periodically update the lists of substances in order to guarantee the correct use of raw materials in the manufacture of personal hygiene products, cosmetics and perfumes.

According to RDC No. 29, of June 1, 2012, which lists the preservative substances allowed for personal hygiene products, cosmetics and perfumes. One of the mentioned preservatives is the metal Titanium, presented in other formulas as Silver chloride, deposited in titanium dioxide, having its maximum concentration

authorized by legislation 0.004% (calculated as silver chloride). It has its limitations, such as 20% AgCl (w/w) in TiO₂. This preservative is restricted for children under 3 years of age, and in products for oral hygiene and in products for the eyes and lips. This makes it difficult to manufacture some isolated cosmetics, considering that this same preservative, Titanium, cannot be in cosmetics that are directly in contact with the mucosa and has its limitations regarding the minimum age.

2.13.6. RDC N° 48, March 16, 2006.

Provides for the approval of the technical regulation on the list of substances that cannot be used in personal hygiene products, cosmetics and perfumes.

It is considered one of the functions of the Sanitary Surveillance, to maintain as a basis the prevention of health problems, the population the regulatory action to guarantee the quality of products and services, which includes the approval of norms and their respective updates, as well as the due inspections of their application, thus being considered as personal hygiene products, cosmetics and perfumes, they must remain safe under normal or foreseeable conditions for their users.

The use in cosmetic products of substances in categories I and II of the IARC (which is the international agency for research on cancer), as well as other international references, which are also classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic or toxic for reproduction in the general. Continuing the list, some possible metals are pointed out, but the current legislation does not indicate their percentages of use, it only prohibits them, as is the case of heavy metals Arsenic, Lead, cadmium, Mercury and its compounds.

With this, it is valid to point out the fragility of some Brazilian legislation as well as the same one addressed, since the same metals that are cited and addressed in this resolution can be pointed out in other lists, remaining free of exceptions.

2.14. Comparison between Brazilian and international legislation for cosmetic products

The European Union legislation cited in (Annex IV of the EU Directive) allows the use of oxide green and hydroxide of Cr (III) as dyes in formulations in the cosmetic field as is normally found, and these dyes may have Cr (VI) which are not allowed by legislation in the same country, on the other hand it may lead to divergences regarding (Annex II) (EU, 1976, 2009) where it says that the products that were marketed with this substance cannot go to the sales circuit (DIAS & RAU, 2013; BOCCA et al., 2014).

Table 3: Comparison between the limit of contaminants allowed for lipsticks in Brazil, USA and European Union

Substances	Brazil (ANVISA)	USA (FDA)	European Union
arsenic	Prohibited	Variable limits according to the dye	Prohibited
Lead	(up to 3ppm as an impurity in dyes)	Variable limits according to the dye	Prohibited
Cadmium	Prohibited	There is no set limit	Prohibited
Chrome	(up to 20ppm as an impurity in dyes)	Permitted in the form of dye	Prohibited
Aluminum	Prohibited	Permitted in the form of dye	Permitted in the form of dye
Manganese	Prohibited	Permitted in the form of dye	Permitted in the form of dye
Titanium	Permitted in the form of dye	Permitted in the form of dye	Permitted in the form of dye
Mercury	Permitted in the form of dye	Variable limits according to the dye	Prohibited
Phthalate	Permitted in the	There is no set limit	Prohibited

Source: DIAS & RAU, 2013

2.15. Discussion

The presence of metallic substances in lip products has become an issue of concern, therefore, through a quantification study. Liu et al. (2013) measured the concentration of lead and eight other metals in samples of lip products and assessed the potential health risks related to the estimated consumption of these metals. Most of the lip products tested contained high concentrations of titanium and aluminum. All products examined had detectable manganese. Lead was detected in 24 products (75%), with an average concentration of 0.36 ± 0.39 ppm, including one sample with 1.32 ppm.

The authors concluded that the safety of cosmetics should be evaluated not only by the presence of substances dangerous to health, but by the frequency of use and consequent exposure to the contaminating substance. Although metal concentrations in lip products have been reported across studies around the world, the interpretation of how reported concentrations may be related to potential health risk is still a challenge (Liu et al., 2013).

The presence of toxic metals in lip cosmetics was addressed by Maehata et al. (2015). This study evaluated three brands of short-lasting commercial lipsticks, considering red and pink, and considering low, medium and high cost. The authors noticed the difference in the amount of metallic element both between the colors (red and pink) and between the price ranges, that is, there is no guarantee that the price will determine greater or lesser quality in the product, considering that the lipstick of high cost showed a higher amount of nickel.

Marta et al. (2017) conducted a study to determine the presence of metals in lipsticks sold in Brazil. This study looked at different lipstick brands. The data obtained in the study can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Element concentration ranges determined in lipstick samples.

Element	Concentrations found in the samples ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$)
As	0,001 until 0,080
Pb	0,010 until 0,2
Cd	<0,01 until 0,03
Cr	<0,01 until 2,5
Hg	<0,01 until 0,2
Al	<0,01 until 4.500
Mn	<0,1 until 40
Ti	0,9 until 100

Fonte: Adaptado de MARTA *et al.*, 2017).

According to Marta et al. (2017), in European legislation, all elements studied are prohibited, except aluminum, which is allowed in dye, whereas in American legislation, all are allowed in the form of dye with variable limits. The authors indicate that these results demonstrate that certain contaminants are present in lipstick samples, although prohibited by Brazilian legislation, which can cause various diseases, harming the population that uses them.

In a study carried out by Batista, Augusto and Pereira-Filho (2016) the presence of lead in cosmetic samples was observed. Lead was previously detected in 25 lipstick samples, lead concentrations ranged from 0.11 to 4.48 mg/kg. While in a study by Al-Saleh et al. (2009) reported that four brands of lipstick exceeded the FDA pre-established lead limit as impurities (20 ppm). The United States FDA has approved the use of mica (silicate minerals that provide a shiny, sparkling appearance) in good manufacturing practices with a lead content not exceeding 20 ppm in drugs, dentifrices, and externally used cosmetics (USFDA, 2002).

These heavy metals should not be added to cosmetics during the manufacturing process as an ingredient formula. However, it is possible to observe the presence of these substances in lipsticks in different studies. The existence of heavy metals was believed to be due to the natural occurrences of these heavy metals in color additives, as well as contamination in the lipstick manufacturing process. During the manufacturing process, sources of heavy metals can come from lead and solder paints in manufacturing equipment and also from lead-contaminated dust from the manufacturing environment.

To ensure safety and effectiveness, cosmetic products are regulated and controlled around the world. However, the harmonization of laws dealing with cosmetics is far from being achieved and regulatory frameworks vary greatly between countries, making it practically impossible for a global industry to sell the same product in all markets (AMPARO & ALBERTO, 2007)

They can contain over 10,000 ingredients related to many diseases such as cancer, birth defects, developmental and reproductive harm. Knowing such toxic effects, FDA (2011), completely banned the presence of nine ingredients, including coal tar colors, formaldehyde, glycol ethers, lead, mercury, phenylenediamine, phthalates in cosmetic products.

Exposure to metals can occur through diet, medications, environmental exposure and use of cosmetics (ADAL & TARABAR, 2013). For example, underarm antiperspirant use was investigated by Darbre (2003) as a possible cause of breast cancer. The basis for breast carcinogenesis may be due to the binding of various chemical constituents including metals to DNA and promoting the growth of damaged cells, which is why some guidelines prohibit the use or presence of heavy metals such as: Cd, Co, Cr, Ni and Pb considered impurities in the preparation of cosmetics.

The Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (2012) stated that exposure to more than 0.005 ppm of cadmium is likely to be hazardous to human health. However, the exposure level that is well thought of as a high limit

is diverse because the cadmium effect can increase or decrease depending on other factors such as form, type and duration of exposure..

Although metal concentrations in cosmetic products have been reported by studies conducted in many countries, the interpretation of how these reported concentrations may be related to potential health risk is a challenge (ADEPOJU-BELLO et al., 2012. AL-SALEH, AL-ENAZI & SHINWARI, 2009; BRANDÃO et al., 2012). The increase in health awareness and the increased availability of cosmetic products in different markets calls the attention of researchers in order to find adverse effects related to contamination by heavy metals (SAEED et al., 2010; BARAKAT, 2011).

Therefore, lip cosmetics, as they are products for oral use, we can consider that the ingestion of the product is almost certain. The results described above in this chapter showed the presence of toxic metallic elements, and, although there are current legislations of the Brazilian health agency that deals with cosmetics, it is also necessary a legislative tool that considers metallic elements in cosmetics to ensure the preservation of the public health. In order to fully evaluate the safety of cosmetic products containing metals, post-marketing surveillance and monitoring are necessary, mainly through Cosmetovigilance, which aims at a set of activities related to the detection, evaluation, understanding and prevention of adverse events and any other problems. associated with cosmetic products.

An example of the application of Cosmetovigilance is the Sanitary Surveillance Center of São Paulo (CVS/SP), which makes available to the population and health professionals an electronic notification form that facilitates communication by users about problems arising from the use of cosmetics. , such as technical complaints or undesirable effects. Then, based on the analysis of the notifications received, it is possible to monitor the effects resulting from the use of cosmetics, personal care products or perfumes that are available on the market, as well as monitoring compliance with current legislation (prohibition of substances, labeling, among others).) (BRASIL, 2018).

Resolution RDC n° 332 of 1st. of December 2005, determines that responsible manufacturing/importing companies in Mercosur must implement a Cosmetovigilance system. This system should cover the registration of reports of occurrences of adverse events/evaluation, the registration of the adopted measures and the notification to ANVISA. Through the Sanitary Surveillance Notification System (Notivisa), registered companies/institutions, health professionals and the citizen (by means of a citizen form) can make notifications of situations that imply a risk to the health of the consumer, thus, according to the ANVISA, regulatory actions may be applied such as modification of labeling information, publication of alerts and guidelines for rational use, review of ingredients used and their concentrations for use in cosmetics, up to the withdrawal of batches from the market, suspension of the product and cancellation of the record.

Therefore, verification of compliance with specifications should be seen as a necessary requirement to guarantee the quality, safety and efficacy of the product, and not just as a regulatory requirement (BRASIL, 2008).

3. Conclusion

The work presented addresses a currently discussed topic, where every day several studies are carried out and published through electronic articles, journals and books. Knowing the possible contaminants in lip products and the toxicity of these substances are important tools to assess the safety of these cosmetic products and for them to be used safely without exposure to substances that are harmful to health. In addition, this review study made it possible to survey the currently available legislation, continuous use of these contaminated cosmetics can result in an increase in some levels of metals in the human body beyond acceptable limits. These findings call for mandatory regular testing programs to verify the concentration of metals in cosmetic products in order to limit their increase in the body and thus protect the health of consumers. Additional efforts are needed to educate users and the general public about the dangers of using these products outside the specifications outlined by regulatory agencies.

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